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Research Article

KNOWLEDGE ATTITUDE AND PRACTICE ABOUT ORAL HYGIENE: A SURVEY OF MEDICAL STUDENTS QAMC BAHAWALPUR

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Abstract:

Introduction: Oral hygiene is a practice conducive to maintaining oral health and preventing disease process through regular brushing, flossing and other means at hand. It is a part and parcel of oral health. It is a major component of systemic health and touches every aspect of our lives. Oral and systemic health are reciprocally related to each other.

Despite its importance oral health is often taken for-grated. It should rather be taken seriously as oral health greatly influences overall health and well-being of an individual.

Objective: The objective of the study isto determine the knowledge, attitude and practice of medical students of QAMC BWP Pakistan towards their oral hygiene.

Materials and Methods

Study setting: The study was carried out in medical students of Quaid -e-Azam medical college Bahawalpur.

Study Design: Cross-sectional observational descriptive study.

Duration: 2nd March 2019 to 2nd May 2019.

Sampling population: Medical student from 1st year to 5th year of QAMC BWP during study period were included.

Sample size: sample was 200 students.

Sampling technique: stratification.

Inclusion criteria: Both genders.

Exclusion Criteria: unwilling students.

Ethical issues: informed consent was taken from all participants (verbal).

Data collection: Data was collected through preformed presented questionnaire that comprises of two parts. First part includes demographic variables as name, age, and second part consists of study variables knowledge and practice of oral hygiene.

Data analysis: data obtained from questionnaire was analyzed manually. Frequencies were calculated, also tables and figures were made.

Results: In our study a sample of 200 students of QAMC was taken .The survey revealed that 99.5% cleaned their teeth out of which 97% used brush and paste, 60.5% of them brushed once a day. Time used by 55% of students for brushing is 1-2 min. 68% used combined method of brushing, 79% used soft bristle toothbrush.

The survey revealed that 44% of students clean their tongue regularly and 62.5% also cleaned their gums .Mouth wash is the most commonly used secondary method to prevent plaque. About 82.5% know that oral and systemic health are related to each other. Only 34% of students had ever visited a dentist. 40% of students experienced bad breath. When asked about habits 64% used tea and 3% used beetle nuts in routine.

Conclusion: All the students had adequate level of knowledge about oral hygiene.

Key words: Oral hygiene, Knowledge, Attitude, Practice, Medical Students.

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INTRODUCTION:

Oral hygiene is a practice conducive to maintaining oral health and preventing disease process through regular brushing, flossing and other means at hand. It is a part and parcel of oral health (1)

Oral health is defined as, “standard of health of oral and related tissues which enables an individual to eat, speak and socialize without active disease, discomfort or embarrassment and which contributes to general well-being (2)

It is a major component of systemic health and touches every aspect of our lives. Oral and systemic health are reciprocally related to each other. So, systemic diseases will exaggerate if oral diseases are left untreated and vice versa. Good oral health helps to reduce incidence of stroke and heart diseases. Similarly, many systemic diseases have oral manifestations (3).

Despite its importance oral health is often taken for-granted. It should rather be taken seriously as oral health greatly influences overall health and well-being of an individual (2).

Unhealthy and unhygienic habits, like use of tobacco, beetle nuts, smoking, pan, taking tea and lack of dental specialist care, have deteriorating effects (4) on oral health including halitosis, dental plaque, dental caries, gingivitis, stomatitis, periodontitis and oral carcinoma (5)

Oral diseases are considered to be a social stigma. As oral health greatly influences our social and psychological health (6). Its effects individuals and community in terms of pain, suffering, functional impairment and generally reduces quality of life. As these diseases are expensive to be treated, timely preventive measures should be taken including flossing, regular brushing, use of fluoride toothpaste and other available techniques (7).

Taking into account the facts, WHO has introduced Recommend Oral Self Care (ROSC) for year 2020, with following goals; tooth brushing more than once a day, lesser consumption of sugar containing snacks once daily or rarely, and regular use of fluoride containing tooth pastes (5).

This study was to evaluate the knowledge and practice of oral hygiene and to access factors associated with oral hygiene among various students of Quaid-e-Azam medical college, Bahawalpur, Pakistan so that the results may help us in future planning of awareness campaign.

Considering the fact that medical students are more knowledgeable and aware of health problems, they are thought to have better approach towards their own oral health. Despite that oral health is grossly inadequate among many doctors. Through this undergraduate study it is rational for students in field of public health care to develop and modify their approach towards their own oral health.

METHODOLOGY:

Study setting: The study was carried out in medical students of Quaid -e-Azam medical college Bahawalpur.

Study Design: Cross-sectional observational descriptive study

Duration: 2nd March 2019 to 2nd May 2019

Sampling population: Medical student from 1st year to 5th year of Quaid -e-Azam medical college during study period were included.

Sample size: sample was 200 students

Sampling technique: stratification

Inclusion criteria: Both genders

Exclusion Criteria: Unwilling students

Ethical issues: Informed consent was taken from all participants (verbal)

Data collection: A pre-designed and pre-tested questionnaire was used for the collection of data in this research. The questionnaire consisted of two parts. In first part questions about bio data were asked and in second part questions about the actual research were asked after taking their verbal consent. Out of total 200 students, 40 students were taken from each year (20 males and 20 females). Class interval was made, and first roll number was taken by drawing lottery, and afterwards as per class interval.

The students with roll numbers next to those who were not willing to provide information were asked to fill questionnaire. The questionnaires were given to them in morning and were collected back after 2 hours on the same day.

Data analysis: data obtained from questionnaire was analyzed manually. Frequencies were calculated, also tables and figures were made.

RESULTS:

In this study a sample of 200 students of QAMC was taken. The survey revealed that almost all participants i.e. 99.5% (Males:100%, Females:99%) cleaned their teeth (Table No.1), out of which 97% (Males:96%, Females:98%) used brush and paste while rest used brush and powder, 60.5%(Males:64%, Females:57%) of them brushed once a day while 35.5%(Males:32%, Females:39%) brushed twice a day. On asking about the type of brushing method 68%(Males:55%, Females:84%) answered with combined method while about 9%(Males:15%, Females:3%) used vertical method of brushing. As far as bristle consistency of toothbrush is concerned 79%(Males:75%, Females:82%) used soft bristle and 16%(Males:19%, Females:13%) used hard bristle (Graph No.1 and Graph No.2). Tooth-brush changing frequency varied from every 2month 51%(Males:55%, Females:48%) to every 6month 10%(Males:8%, Females:12%) (Graph No.3 and Graph No.4).

Regarding the choice of tooth paste, the survey revealed that 80%(Males:78%, Females:82%) of students choose it personally while 2.5%(Males:4%, Females:1%) took to social media for help, about 29.5%(Males:31%, Females:28%) used salted toothpaste whereas 28.5%(Males:26%, Females:31%) used medicated toothpaste (Fig. No.3 and Fig. No.4).

Maximum amount of time used by students for brushing 1-2min is 55 % (Males: 47%, Females: 63%) and 17 % (Males: 19%, Females: 14%) took less than 1min for brushing (Fig. No.3 and Fig. No.4).

Furthermore, it was revealed that 26% students (Males:25.6%, Females:18%) suffered from difficulties during brushing; including bleeding 15% (Males:15%, Females:12%), sensitivity and gag 3%(Males:3%, Females:3%) and pain1%(Males: 1%, Females: 1%) (Fig. No.5 and Fig. No.6)

Tongue cleaning is one of the prime components of oral hygiene.44% of students (Males: 36%, Females: 51%) clean their tongue regularly and 62.5% (Males: 68%, Females: 57%) also cleaned their gums (Table No.1).

Other than brushing there are a lot of methods which are being employed in maintaining oral hygiene and among them mouth wash is the most commonly used secondary method while 4 %

(Males: 1%, Females: 7%) used nails to prevent plague (Fig No.7 and Fig No.8).

The survey further revealed that only 5% students (Males: 4%, Females: 6%) wore braces. Most of the students 57.5 % (Males: 40%, Females: 75%) started their dental care during childhood while 2.5% (Males: 1%, Females: 4%) started at age of 20.

Most of the students about 82.5 % (Males: 73%, Females: 92%) know that oral and systemic health are related to each other (Table No.1).

When asked about cause of dental caries 83% of students (Males: 82%, Females: 84%) think that caries are caused by chocolates and sweets and 46.5% students (Males: 51%, Females: 42%) think that brushing alone can prevent them (Table No.1). Majority of the students 99% check their teeth for abnormalities. Only 34% of students (Males: 29%, Females: 39%) had ever visited a dentist among them 12% students (Males: 10%, Females: 14%) had general visit while 22% of students (Males: 19%, Females: 25%) visited when suffering from any dental problem (Table No.1)

Study revealed that 40% of students (Males: 50%, Females:34%) experienced bad breath. When asked about habits 64% (Males: 68%, Females: 60%) used tea and 3 % (Males: 6%, Females: 0%) used beetle nuts in routine (Table No.1).

15% of students (Males: 12%, Females: 8%) had undergone scaling while only 3% (Males: 4%, Females 2%) had artificial implants (Table No.1)

DISCUSSION:

The study was conducted to check awareness and attitude of medical students towards their oral health and hygiene. Total 200 students were interviewed, the results were compiled and compared with the researches carried out in Karachi, India, China, Jordan and Korea.

Detailed analysis revealed that 99.5% of students cleaned their teeth while a study conducted in Karachi showed that 92.7% of the students cleaned their teeth (13). Our results were similar to a study done in India showed that 72.6% people cleaned their teeth. Majority of the students (97%) used brush and paste which is similar to the results to a study done in India in which 100% of the people questioned used brush and paste to clean their teeth. Approximately 88.3% of the people cleaned their teeth twice a day which is in contrast to a study done in India which found only 44.1% people cleaned their teeth twice daily (11). About 23% of people use horizontal method of brushing which is very similar to a study conducted in china which

showed that 23.6% of people employ the same technique (12).

Soft bristle is the most commonly used type of tooth brush (79%) and second is hard bristle i.e. 16%. The study from India showed contrasting results that only 35.8% used soft bristle and 5% used hard bristle (11), this is similar to a study conducted in Jordan which showed that 12% people used hard bristle tooth brush (10). Although it is recommended to change your tooth brush monthly but majority of the students 38% changed their tooth brush in every 3 months. This is in contrast to the results of the studies done in India and china 52.5% and 64.5% of the students changed their tooth brush every 3 months respectively (11,12).

According to American Dental Association, brushing time should be at least 2 minutes and no less. While the survey showed that only 28% of students brushed for 2 to 3 minutes and 55% for less than 2 minutes. Another study in India showed that 38.3 % students brushed for 1 to 3 minutes and in contrast to 47.6% for 3 to 5 minutes which is better as compared to study done here(11).

Out of many problems encountered during brushing bleeding is the most frequent one (13%) which is similar to a study done in Karachi i.e. 20% (13). Another study showed that 64% students in China and 22% students in Jordan had same the difficulty during brushing (12, 10). 40% of the students complained about the bad breath while 6.3% students in Karachi 36% in Korea and 13% in china had the same complaint (13, 8).

Tongue cleaning is one of the prime component of the oral hygiene. 44% of the students clean their tongue regularly which is contrasting to the results found in a study done in India that 80% of the students cleaned their tongue. The reason behind the gap is the because of less priority given to it. The reason for which is the lack of knowledge about the significance of the tongue hygiene (11).

Other than brushing there a lot of methods which are being employed in maintaining oral hygiene and among them mouth wash is the most commonly used secondary method. 43.5% of students use mouth wash while a study conducted in Karachi showed similar results that 41% of students used mouth wash (13). Another study conducted found that 24.1% students in India and 13% students in china used mouth wash. 7% of students use floss and according studies conducted 12.5% students in India and 3.45% in china used floss. Most of the people think that they don't need mouth wash after brushing and they often feel its taste bad (11, 12).

When asked about the causes of the dental caries 83% of students think that caries are caused by chocolates and sweets while 55.5% students in china holds the same opinion (12).

Majority (99%) of the students check their teeth for abnormalities. Similar results were found in studies in Jordan (79%) and Korea (78%). Only 34% of students had ever visited a dentist similarly 57% students in Karachi and 79.2% in India had visited a dentist (10, 13, 8).

It is evident from the study that medical students being health professionals should have a better knowledge, understanding and approach towards oral health and hygiene. It is very obvious that there is a lot of room of improvement in this aspect, so measures and steps should be taken to create awareness about oral health among students. Seminars and workshops should be organized that might help them to achieve basic knowledge and skills to maintain their oral hygiene and health.

TABLE NO.1

Knowledge, Attitude & Practice about Oral Hygiene of Medical Students of QAMC BWP

Variable	Response	Males	Females
Do you clean your teeth?	Yes	100%	99%
	No	0%	1%
Do you clean your tongue?	Yes	36%	51%
	No	64%	49%
Do you clean your gums?	Yes	68%	57%
	No	32%	43%
Do you wear braces	Yes	4%	6%
	No	96%	94%
Do you know oral health is related to systemic health?	Yes	73%	92%
	No	27%	8%
Is it possible to prevent gum diseases with brushing alone?	Yes	51%	42%
	No	49%	58%
How often do you check your teeth for abnormalities?	Daily	36%	41%
	Monthly	38%	38%
	Yearly	26%	21%
Do you visit a dentist?	Yes	29%	39%
	General visit	10%	14%
	while suffering	19%	25%
Have you ever experienced bad breath?	Yes	50%	34%
	No	50%	61%
Do you have any of the following habits?	Beetle nut	6%	0%
	Smoking	14%	1%
	Pan	0%	0%
	Tea	68%	60%
	None	12%	36%
Have you undergone any dental procedures?	Scaling	12%	8%
	Filling	14%	13%
	Root canal	10%	12%
	Implants	4%	2%
	None	60%	65%

FIGURE 1: Attitude of female students regarding oral hygiene

FIGURE 2: Attitude of male students regarding oral hygiene

CONCLUSION:

The research has demonstrated the majority the students had adequate level of knowledge about oral health and hygiene. But relatively they show low levels of practice. Factors like age and gender has not shown to have much influence on the level of knowledge and practice among students. There is a lot of room for improvement so measures (e.g. seminars and workshops) should be taken to create awareness and to help them achieve basic knowledge and skills to maintain their oral health and hygiene.

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ANNEXURE

Name:

Age:

Gender:

Medical school year:

1. Do you have any of the following habits?

Beetle nuts

Smoking

Pan

2. Do you clean your teeth? Yes/No

3. How do you clean your teeth?

Brush and paste

Brush and powder

Others datur, finger, miswak, charcoal powder or mouth wash

4. How often do you brush your teeth?

Once

Twice

More than twice

Sometimes

5. What type of brushing method do you employ?

Vertical

Horizontal

Combined

6. What type of toothbrush you use

Child size

Hard bristle

Soft bristle

Electric

7. What kind of paste you use

Salted

Non salted

8. How much time do you take to brush your teeth?

Less than 1 min

1 2 mins

2 3 mins

9. Do you feel difficulty while brushing

Yes/no

If yes, what do you feel?

Pain

Sensitivity

Bleeding

Bad taste

What measures do you take to relieve it?

10. Do you clean your tongue

Yes/no

11. Do you clean your gums

Yes/no

12. What type of secondary methods do you employ to prevent plaques

Floss

Interdental floss brush

Tooth picks

Pins

Nails

Leaves

Any other

None

13. Do you use braces? Yes/no

14. What time did you start dental care?

Childhood

10 year of age

Teenage

20 year of age

15. Do you know oral health is related to systemic health? Yes /No

16. Do you what causes/habits lead to dental caries?

Chocolates

Sweet

List any

17. Is it possible to prevent gum disease with brushing alone? Yes/No

18. How often do you check your teeth for any abnormality? Daily, monthly, yearly

19. How often do you change your tooth brush?

Every 2 month

Every 3 month

Every 6 month

Every year

20. Do you visit a dentist? Yes /no

If yes

General visit When in pain

If general how often

Every month

Every 3rd month

Every 6 month

Yearly

21. Have you ever felt bad breath? Yes/No

If yes how often you feel it? Weekly, Monthly, Yearly

How bad is it? Not much, bad, very bad

22. Does your Gums bleed while brushing?

23. Do you know any type of systemic disorder that has dental manifestation?

List any